

Erasmus JOBS

Report T1.5- Analysis and List of common obtained Skills

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With the support of Erasmus+

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Introduction

The ErasmusJobs Project¹, in particular the task of IO1 - A comprehensive Competence Profile, is devoted to define which skills are provided by an Erasmus+ mobility abroad, map the skills employers seek and make a comparative analysis of the two, highlighting the concrete benefits that Erasmus+ brings for participants. Furthermore, it will produce a competence booklet, a report, and policy recommendations on how to support Erasmus+ Alumni.

This document shows what transversal competences do Erasmus+ students have.

At a later stage/report we will analyze how do competences from Erasmus+ students translate into competences employers need.

In this report we include the analysis of surveys done by Erasmus students from the 4 universities in the ErasmusJobs project consortium:

- Masaryk University (MSK)
- Universidad de Alcala (UAH)
- Université de Mons (UMONS)
- Università degli Studi di Roma "Tor Vergata" (TORVERGATA)

We have collected data about our students that joined the Erasmus Mobility program in the last two years, focusing the attention on the survey collected by the Erasmus Agency at the end of the visiting period. Thanks to the common Mobility Tool used by all the 4 universities to retrieve data from Erasmus students, we have had the possibility to study the dataset from a common point of view. We have focused on the questions related with skills and competences.

The participation of students from the different universities are shown below.

Partner University	Nº Students
Masaryk University,	1031
Universidad de Alcala	448
Université de Mons	726
Università degli Studi di Roma "Tor Vergata"	1141

Skills questionnaire

Data are collected from the Mobility Tool of the Erasmus Agency and are related to our students that joined the Erasmus Students Mobility Program and the Erasmus Traineeship Mobility program in the last two years (outgoing Students).

¹ <http://erasmusjobs.org>

We focused the attention on the questions of the Erasmus survey that attain to the experience and the skills related to the mobility program for our students selecting the following different 30 questions shown in the table below.

ID	Survey question
1	Think logically and draw conclusions (analytical skills)
2	Find solutions in difficult or challenging contexts (problem-solving skills)
3	Plan and carry out my learning independently
4	Use the internet, social media and pcs , e.g. For my studies, work and personal activities
5	Develop an idea and put it into practice
6	See the value of different cultures
7	Cooperate in teams
8	Plan and organise tasks and activities
9	Express myself creatively
10	I am more confident and convinced of my abilities
11	I know better my strengths and weaknesses
12	I am more able to adapt to and act in new situations
13	I am more able to think and analyse information critically
14	I am more tolerant towards other persons' values and behaviour
15	I am more open-minded and curious about new challenges
16	I intend to participate more actively in social and political life of my community
17	I am more interested in knowing what happens in the world daily
18	I am more able to reach decisions
19	I am more able to cooperate with people from other backgrounds and cultures
20	I am more interested in European topics
21	I feel more European
22	I am more aware of social and political concepts like democracy, justice, equality, citizenship, civil rights
23	I have increased my sector- or field-specific skills
24	I believe that my chances to get a new or better job have increased
25	I have a clearer idea about my professional career aspirations and goals
26	I have better opportunities for traineeships or student jobs in my home country
27	I am better capable of taking over work tasks with high responsibility after my stay abroad
28	I can easily imagine working abroad at some point in the future
29	I can easily imagine working in the country where I did my Erasmus+ period in the future
30	I would like to work in an international context

Every Erasmus student valued each question following the next scale range:

- Strongly agree
- Rather agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Rather disagree
- Strongly disagree

To obtain a mean value from the qualitative marks above, a scale from -2 to +2 points are assigned to each student answer. The mean values ranged from -2 to +2 has been transformed in the more visual 0 to 10 values. Next table shows the mean values obtained for the Erasmus experience of all outgoing Erasmus students for each partner university.

UNIVERSITY	Mean value of the Erasmus Experience
TORVERGATA	8,04
UMONS	7,31
UAH	7,95
MSK	6,28

Taken into account the data shown in the above table it can be said that in general students consider very valuable the European mobility experience. However, the range and value spans for the students' answers are very different. The values are shown in the table and graphically in a figure below.

UNIVERSITY	Min	Mean value of the Erasmus Experience	MAX
TORVERGATA	7,1	8,04	9,01
UMONS	6,09	7,31	8,52
UAH	6,73	7,95	9,06
MSK	4,74	6,28	7,43

As there are differences in the qualification of all the questions, to unbiased the information we have arrange the mean of all universities to a common value and equalize the span of data to uniform the information given by the students of different universities/countries. It is out of the scope to analyse the reason for these different satisfaction values of Erasmus mobilities.

Finally, the different values are re-centered in the Mean value of 7,40 considering a span range from -1,23 to 1,11 for the difference of values in answers. These corrected values are obtained by the following formula:

$$(\text{answer_value} - \text{current_mean}) * (\text{max_min_corrected_span}) / (\text{max_min_current_span}) + \text{corrected_mean}$$

Data Analysis

The main goal was to identify the most important changes for students after the mobility program. The experience of mobility abroad is greatly valued, but we would like to point out those aspects more highlighted.

Trying to equalize the data from different countries, we have matched the mean values for the different universities in order to try to extract better which are the skills more valued by Erasmus students.

The next table shows the questions sorted with the obtained weighted scores from the whole dataset.

Table. Sorted questions – obtained skills

Survey question - Ranking order	Score
1. I am more able to adapt to and act in new situations	8,0
2. I am more open-minded and curious about new challenges	7,9
3. I know better my strengths and weaknesses	7,8
4. See the value of different cultures	7,8
5. Plan and carry out my learning independently	7,8
6. I am more able to cooperate with people from other backgrounds and cultures	7,8
7. I am more confident and convinced of my abilities	7,7
8. I would like to work in an international context	7,7
9. Find solutions in difficult or challenging contexts (problem-solving skills)	7,7
10. I can easily imagine working abroad at some point in the future	7,6
11. I believe that my chances to get a new or better job have increased	7,6
12. I am more able to reach decisions	7,6
13. I am more able to think and analyse information critically	7,6
14. I am more tolerant towards other persons' values and behaviour	7,5
15. Plan and organise tasks and activities	7,5
16. I have increased my sector- or field-specific skills	7,4

17. I am better capable of taking over work tasks with high responsibility after my stay abroad	7,4
18. Think logically and draw conclusions (analytical skills)	7,3
19. I am more interested in knowing what happens in the world daily	7,3
20. Develop an idea and put it into practice	7,2
21. Use the internet, social media and pcs , e.g. For my studies, work and personal activities	7,2
22. I am more interested in European topics	7,2
23. Cooperate In Teams	7,1
24. Express Myself Creatively	7,1
25. I Have A Clearer Idea About My Professional Career Aspirations And Goals	7,0
26. I Am More Aware Of Social And Political Concepts Like Democracy, Justice, Equality, Citizenship, Civil Rights	6,9
27. I Have Better Opportunities For Traineeships Or Student Jobs In My Home Country	6,9
28. I Intend To Participate More Actively In Social And Political Life Of My Community	6,8
29. I Can Easily Imagine Working In The Country Where I Did My Erasmus+ Period In The Future	6,7
30. I Feel More European	6,7

Grouping the questions in different criteria (self-esteem, personal resilience and international dimension), we can observe the following:

In the top positions of the ranking, there are several questions related with self-esteem and personal resilience:

1. I am more able to adapt to and act in new situations
2. I am more open-minded and curious about new challenges
3. I know better my strengths and weaknesses
5. Plan and carry out my learning independently
7. I am more confident and convinced of my abilities
9. Find solutions in difficult or challenging contexts (problem-solving skills)

Others items that are top-ranked are related to internationalization:

4. See the value of different cultures
6. I am more able to cooperate with people from other backgrounds and cultures
8. I would like to work in an international context

On the contrary, surprisingly, the European citizenship values are ranked in the last positions, which is one main goal of Erasmus mobilities.

Additionally, to the mean score values in each question, there were included the max and min values for the different university mean values, trying to give the reader an idea of the variability of that question for the students filling the questionnaire.

List of common obtained Skills

Looking at the results of the analysis done in the questionnaires filled by Erasmus students, we focus now our attention in the skills that are perceived as enhancing employability, in order to seek later a better matching with the skills needed by employers: We differentiate 5 groups of skills:

- Adaptability skills (AD)
- Teamwork skills (TW)
- Career orientation skills (CO)
- Managerial skills (MA)
- Personal skills. (PE)

The next table assigns to each survey question the 1 or 2 group of skills more related with employability.

Survey question - Ranking order sorted	AD	TW	CO	MA	PE
1. I am more able to adapt to and act in new situations	X				
2. I am more open-minded and curious about new challenges	X				
3. I know better my strengths and weaknesses					X
4. See the value of different cultures					X
5. Plan and carry out my learning independently					X
6. I am more able to cooperate with people from other backgrounds and cultures		X			
7. I am more confident and convinced of my abilities					X
8. I would like to work in an international context		X			
9. Find solutions in difficult or challenging contexts (problem-solving skills)			X		
10. I can easily imagine working abroad at some point in the future		X			
11. I believe that my chances to get a new or better job have increased			X		
12. I am more able to reach decisions				X	X
13. I am more able to think and analyse information critically			X	X	
14. I am more tolerant towards other persons' values and behaviour				X	X
15. Plan and organise tasks and activities				X	
16. I have increased my sector- or field-specific skills					

Survey question - Ranking order sorted	AD	TW	CO	MA	PE
17. I am better capable of taking over work tasks with high responsibility after my stay abroad				X	
18. Think logically and draw conclusions (analytical skills)			X	X	
19. I am more interested in knowing what happens in the world daily					X
20. Develop an idea and put it into practice		X			
21. Use the internet, social media and pcs , e.g. For my studies, work and personal activities					X
22. I am more interested in European topics					X
23. Cooperate in teams		X			
24. Express myself creatively					X
25. I have a clearer idea about my professional career aspirations and goals			X		
26. I am more aware of social and political concepts like democracy, justice, equality, citizenship, civil rights					X
27. I have better opportunities for traineeships or student jobs in my home country			X		
28. I intend to participate more actively in social and political life of my community					X
29. I can easily imagine working in the country where i did my Erasmus+ period in the future			X		
30. I feel more European					X

Finally, we can resume the following set of skills that might be feasible to match with employers' needs.

Conclusions

This document resumes the skills mostly gained by Erasmus mobility experiences.

Abbreviations

TEM	Transnational educational mobility
KSAs	Knowledge, skills and attitudes
IC	Intercultural competence
E+	Erasmus+
ICT	information and communication technology
HEI	Higher Education Institution

Possible Further Analysis (out of scope of the ErasmusJobs project)

Erasmus Student Mobility:

- Country of destination or geographical area
- Area of studying (Economics, Law, Literature, etc...)
- Length of the visiting period
- Size and specialization of the hosting university
- Student's information (age, sex, etc...)

Include students that joined the traineeship mobility program.

Erasmus Traineeship Mobility

- Country of destination or geographical area
- Area of studying (Economics, Law, Literature, etc...)
- Length of the visiting period
- Type and size of Hosting Institution
- Student's information (age, sex, etc...)

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